

From Xerogels to Aerogels: synthesis of porous oxyfluoride glass-ceramics for optical applications

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ABSTRACT

Rare-earth (RE) ions doped oxyfluoride glass-ceramics (OxGCs) are being widely investigated in the last decades for its potential use in different photonics applications, such as solid-state lasers, white light emitting diodes (wLEDs), solar cells and catalysis, among others. These materials combine the good mechanical, thermal and chemical properties of an oxide glass matrix with the low phonon energy of crystalline fluoride environments ($250\text{-}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and good solubility of RE ions in the fluoride crystals, which reduces non-radiative multiphonon relaxations, increasing the optical efficiency. Moreover, GCs present a high degree of transparency due to the much smaller size of uniformly dispersed nanocrystals (NCs) in the amorphous matrix, less than 100 nm [1,2]. These OxGCs can also be obtained in different forms, such as bulk, coatings or fibers.

One of the synthesis routes to obtain bulk OxGCs is the sol-gel method. The SG emerges as an alternative synthesis route at low temperatures, to avoid the drawbacks observed in other routes, such as the melting-quenching (MQ) process. This method permits obtaining more homogeneous and pure materials with higher fluorine content, resulting in high crystalline fraction, around 18 wt% in $80\text{SiO}_2\text{-}20\text{LaF}_3$ compositions [3,4]. However, bulk transparent SG materials are difficult to obtain due to the presence of the residual porosity in the structure and the existence of residual stresses generated during the sintering process [5]. Moreover, the presence of residual OH groups strongly reduces the RE ions luminescence.

To overcome these shortcomings the processing of bulk SG materials must be optimized. The first approximation combines the SG chemistry and the supercritical drying process to obtain $\text{SiO}_2\text{-REF}_3$ composite aerogels partially crystallized with a narrow pore size distribution. This process route is inspired by the drying procedure of silica aerogels under supercritical conditions, followed by adequate thermal treatments to obtain bulk OxGCs. Following this processing route, the synthesis was optimized to obtain bulk monolithic wet-gels, by controlling the synthesis and processing parameters (tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS)/water/ethanol ratio, pH, temperature and reaction time, rate of hydrolysis and condensation, aging time in ethanol, etc). Then, bulk materials were obtained using supercritical drying process under supercritical conditions of ethanol in CO_2 . However, despite the effective synthesis of monolithic crack-free samples, the performed DTA/DSC, FTIR, XRD analysis of the obtained bulk materials, after the different sintering process (temperature and time), revealed that the crystallization was strongly inhibited after the supercritical drying process using ethanol (243 °C and 72 Mpa.).

Therefore, it was necessary to propose a new route to obtain bulk OxGCs, based on the use of transfer charge complexes to synthesize LaF_3 NCs. The NCs obtained this way can be incorporated into a TEOS/water/ethanol solution to obtain sols with $\text{SiO}_2\text{-REF}_3$ composition. These samples can be finally processed following different routes, such as supercritical drying or slow drying + thermal treatment resulting in crack-free bulk OxGCs [6,7]. Preliminary analysis of the materials obtained by this route reveals NCs with mean size ranging 5-8 nm obtained at very low temperature (70 °C),

opening the way to use in composite aerogels.

Keywords: Oxyfluoride glass ceramics; sol-gel; nanocrystal; supercritical drying; transfer charge complex process; optical properties.

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